

5th

European

★ Conference on ★
Pharmaceutics

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Ready for the future: innovative dosage forms and
advanced technologies for modern therapeutics

Porto Portugal
24 - 25 March 2025

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5th European Conference on Pharmaceutics

Innovative dosage forms and advanced technologies for modern therapeutics

24 - 25 March 2025, Porto, Portugal

Dear Colleague,

Following the great success of the past European Conferences on Pharmaceutics, which were held in Reims, Krakow, Bologna and Marseille, it is our great pleasure to announce the fifth congress of this series of international meetings, which will be organised in Porto, Portugal, on 24-25 March 2025. It will be dedicated to "Innovative dosage forms and advanced technologies for modern therapeutics".

The European Conferences on Pharmaceutics are held every two years (in March/April of the uneven years). They are jointly organized by the APGI ("International Society of Drug Delivery Sciences and Technology"), APV ("International Association for Pharmaceutical Technology") and SITELF ("Italian Society of Pharmaceutical Technology and Legislation and Related Disciplines").

Generally, about 600 participants join the conference. Often, one third of them come from industry, one third have permanent position at academia, and one third are young scientists: PhD students & postdocs - the next generation of researchers in our field. The aim is to help bridging the gap between fundamental academic research and industrial applications, offering the opportunity to initiate fruitful exchange and cooperation between university and industry. The conference will be a perfect occasion for young as well as established scientists from all over the world to present their work, discuss most recent scientific findings, network and to share their experience with colleagues. World-wide leading experts in the field will give plenary lectures and invited talks on hot topics. They will give overviews on the current state of the art in the respective domains and outlooks on future perspectives. In addition, new research findings will be presented in the form of short talks, selected from submitted abstracts. Furthermore, poster presentations will give the opportunity to get an update on the most recent discoveries in pharmaceutics and to personally exchange with the authors.

An industrial exhibition will accompany the conference and allow learning about the current trends and newest products in the areas of pharmaceutical ingredients, analytical technologies, equipment, medicinal products, medical devices, contract manufacturing and many other fields.

Please note that all coffee and lunch breaks as well as the welcome reception will be included in the registration fees and will be held in the industrial exhibition & poster presentation area in order to facilitate discussions between participants, exhibitors and presenters.

We are very much looking forward to welcoming you to the 5th European Conference on Pharmaceutics in Porto in 2025!

Juergen Siepmann
President APGI

Sandra Klein
President APV

Paola Minghetti
President SITELF

Chair and programme committee

Chair of the conference

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Influence of Vegetable Oil Type and Concentration on the Rheology, Physical Properties and Sun Protection Factor of Emulsion-Based Lotions

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INTRODUCTION

Skin cancers are the most common group of malignancies diagnosed worldwide, with over 1.5 million new cases estimated in 2022. According to International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), the incidence is predicted to increase by more than 50% from 2020 to 2040, underlining a significant challenge and global public health concern (1). Sunscreens are among the essential tools for protecting the skin from detrimental effects of ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The active ingredients of sunscreens are UV filters that can be classified as inorganic (physical) and organic (chemical). However, the bioaccumulation and environmental impact of cosmetic and dermocosmetic sunscreen products has become a pressing issue. In light of the growing awareness of the photoprotection importance and increasing use of sunscreens, there is a pressing demand for alternative and environmentally sound photoprotective agents (2). Natural oils, valued for their favorable physicochemical properties, emollient and hydrating effects, and antioxidative and anti-inflammatory potential, offer a promising and sustainable alternative to conventional UV protectants. The aim of this study was to evaluate the influence of different types and concentrations of selected vegetable oils on the physical, rheological, and sun protection factor (SPF) properties of emulsion-based lotions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ten emulsion-based lotions were formulated using five different vegetable oils (olive oil, avocado oil, sesame oil, linseed oil, and grape seed oil) at two concentrations (15% and 30%). A control formulation, which contained no added vegetable oil, was also prepared. Dehymuls[®] K (BASF, Germany) served as the absorption base for all formulations. Rheological properties of the lotions were evaluated by obtaining flow curves, and performing amplitude sweep and frequency sweep tests. The occlusive properties of the lotions were assessed using an *in vitro* occlusion test. The SPF of the formulated lotions was determined using a simple spectrophotometric method, as described in previous studies on UV-protective emulsions. To evaluate the physical

stability of the lotions, centrifugal and temperature cycle tests were conducted. After a 30-day storage period at room temperature, rheological properties were re-assessed to determine any structural changes in the emulsions over time.

RESULTS

Over the years, sunscreen development has advanced in affordability, effectiveness, and safety. However, existing challenges present opportunities for further research. Key factors influencing user compliance include the physical and rheological properties of the formulation. Ideal characteristics are low viscosity, aesthetic appeal, small particle size, good solubility, water resistance, a pleasant fragrance, and no residue on clothing. This study aimed to evaluate the physical, rheological, and photoprotective properties of emulsion-based lotions containing selected vegetable oils at two concentrations.

Rheological properties

The rheological characterization of the emulsion lotions began with measuring the apparent viscosities of the selected vegetable oils, which increased in the following order: linseed oil < sesame oil < grape seed oil < olive oil < avocado oil. All formulations exhibited pseudo-plastic flow with thixotropic behavior, indicated by hysteresis loops, which aids in easier application and spreading on the skin. The flow curves were grouped by vegetable oil concentration (Figure 1). The control formulation showed the highest shear stress, while adding 15% vegetable oil reduced shear stress by about half (F1, F3, F5, F9), with the lowest shear stress found in the formulation containing 30% linseed oil (F8). Only the control and the lotion with avocado oil displayed yield stress.

No significant correlation was found between the viscosities of the oils and their corresponding lotions, suggesting that oil-emulsifier interactions influence the rheological behavior. In all formulations, G' values were higher than G'' , indicating solid-like properties dominated. Both G' and G'' increased with frequency, but increasing vegetable oil concentration significantly reduced both values. Lotions with 15% vegetable oil showed higher G' and G'' than the control, with the highest values in the formulation with 15%

olive oil and the lowest in the 30% linseed oil formulation. The increased rigidity in the olive oil formulation may be due to palmitic acid, while the lower rheological parameters in linseed oil can be attributed to its high polyunsaturated fatty acid content.

Figure 1. Change in the value of the shear stress of the tested emulsion lotions in the shear rate range from 0 to 150 s⁻¹

Occlusive factor

The *in vitro* occlusion test showed that all emulsion lotions had high occlusive factor (F) values, above 60%. The addition of vegetable oil increased the occlusive factor, with a statistically significant increase ($p < 0.05$) only in the lotion with 30% olive oil (F2) at 24 and 48 hours, and in the lotion with 30% grape seed oil (F10) at 48 hours (Figure 2). Sunscreens should prevent skin dryness from sunlight, high temperatures, sweat, or seawater. However, occlusive agents can leave a greasy residue and cause an unpleasant sticky feeling, which may reduce user compliance.

Figure 2. Values of the occlusive factor (F) of the investigated emulsion lotions after 24 h and 48 h

UV-protective properties

SPF values for each lotion were calculated by measuring absorbance in the UVB range (290–320 nm). While all formulations with 30% vegetable oil showed higher SPF values than those with 15%, only the lotions with 30% olive oil (SPF = 1.31 ± 0.15), avocado oil (SPF = 3.00 ± 0.41), and linseed oil (SPF = 2.76 ± 0.47) demonstrated UV protection, with SPF values greater than 1. This can be attributed to the chlorophylls, polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), and antioxidants present in these oils.

Physical stability

The emulsion lotions were subjected to centrifugal and temperature cycle tests to assess their stability. No phase separation or significant changes in organoleptic properties were observed, indicating adequate stability of the formulations. After 30 days, no phase separation was evident, however, a reduction in apparent viscosity was observed at a shear rate of 100 s⁻¹, with a statistically significant decrease only in the control formulation, which contained no added vegetable oil (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Apparent viscosities of the tested emulsion lotions at a shear rate of 100 s⁻¹, measured immediately after preparation and after 30 days of storage at room temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Stable emulsion lotions were successfully formulated, while the type and concentration of vegetable oils significantly affected their rheological properties. Formulations with 30% vegetable oil showed higher SPF values than those with 15%, but the SPF was insufficient for standalone sun protection, requiring further investigation with UV filters. All lotions had high occlusive factor values, potentially enhancing skin hydration, though sensory testing is needed due to possible user discomfort. The optimal vegetable oil concentration for UV-protective lotions was 30%, with linseed oil being the most suitable. Further optimization with other vegetable oils and low concentrations of biocompatible UV filters could improve their properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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